

VTA?

Human after all

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We were invited to present our work on assessing the structural resistance of trees at the Association's annual conference at Warwick University in September 2024. What could we say in 20 minutes? A lot and too little.

We chose not to give a technical presentation of the methods we are developing, but rather to explore the professions that have faced assessment and decision-making problems comparable to those in arboriculture – and above all, how they have dealt with them. This article summarises those 20 minutes.

Models of expertise

In the field of the structural assessment of trees, there are two models of expertise, just as there are in the medical field and its models of health. The first is the clinical model, also referred to as the global model. This is the model based on the study of symptoms. It qualifies the resistance of a tree during a structural diagnosis and puts words to phenomena. In international arboriculture, it is often called basic assessment or visual assessment – an unfortunate misnomer, as this approach, when practised methodically, is far from rudimentary and goes well beyond visual observation, encompassing a comprehensive analysis of the tree's condition. The second is the 'technological' model, which quantifies phenomena using measuring devices and gives a value to the resistance of the trees.

Our point is that both models are necessary and that one cannot exist without the other. However, we maintain that it is essential to keep the following two factors in mind:

- Neither model has been statistically validated. We don't know if they really work.
- Today, the technological model seems to dominate the field and the market. However, the clinical model is necessary and must be the least approximate it can possibly be if it is to be truly useful.

Without seeking to value one model over the other, we will focus here on the clinical model. To do this, we need to take a critical look at our current approach.

Many criticisms have been expressed about the 'visual' approach. Most of them are well known and well founded. However, we are going to set out a criticism that is heard less often and yet is experienced by everyone,

and particularly by young practitioners, as a real problem.

Current situation

Today, as arborists, how do we qualitatively assess the structural resistance of a tree? We almost exclusively use Claus Mattheck's visual tree assessment (VTA) method. This method makes us intuitively combine various parameters.

Let's take the example of a much-studied phenomenon: cavities in tree trunks. Here are a number of parameters (which we have divided into three bullet points) that are sometimes used to assess strength:

- The **famous t/R**, which is the percentage of residual wood remaining in the studied trunk (the shell-wall thickness). Unfortunately, this parameter is sometimes the only one used. However, Niklas and Spatz (2014) consider that, in order to talk about resistance, it is necessary to include the lever arm (L) in the equation. For his part, Mattheck included this variable in the calculation of the slenderness factor.
- The **natural adaptations of trees**. Healthy trees react to a reduction in t/R by making geometric changes that can compensate for a local loss of resistance. Trees have the ability to grow in diameter according to their needs. If they have grown, they are more resistant. This is a basic mechanical concept that is now validated – notably because the resistance of a trunk's cross-section increases with the cube of its diameter (D^3). This means that even a small increase in diameter results in a significant gain in structural resistance. There are also other obvious compensatory phenomena, such as structural support elements: reinforcement wood, buttresses and columns, for example.
- We could also assess **the load**, i.e. the forces, acting on a tree – primarily wind forces. Several key factors influence this load: the height of the tree (taller trees experience greater wind forces due to increased leverage), the drag coefficient (which reflects the tree's

Michael Collins, Neil Armstrong and Buzz Aldrin, the crew of Apollo 11. (NASA)

aerodynamic properties), and finally – though this list is not exhaustive – the mass damping, a concept developed by Ken James that explains how trees can mitigate wind loads by desynchronising their movement from wind frequencies.

We could add many other parameters for the qualitative assessment of a tree's structural condition. However, in their current VTA practice, arborists lack a structured framework to analyse tree failure likelihood. They therefore select parameters they deem relevant (some limiting themselves to t/R only), leading to what is called an *intuitive* assessment. This approach seems to be considered normal in the profession today. But should we be satisfied with it?

The best of the best

The famous photograph above shows one of the greatest teams ever assembled. In 1969, NASA brought together Michael Collins, Neil Armstrong and Buzz Aldrin to form an extraordinary team. Each was selected for their very particular skills. As well as being intellectuals (the subject of Aldrin's thesis certainly makes us dizzy), these three boys had exceptional physical attributes and were capable of running marathons as well as taking 10 Gs without blinking an eye. All fighter pilots, they were elite technicians. As war veterans, they had learned to be cool under extreme pressure and were used to difficult situations, and because they were military men, they were used to order, hierarchy and discipline. They were selected from among thousands of elite candidates.

At that time, NASA had committed itself to the colossal Moon landing programme with its memorable slogan: 'Failure is not an option.' How did NASA manage to ensure success? It strictly controlled the human factor through rigorous procedures. The superb team's mission was not to rely on improvisation but to follow carefully designed protocols. Individual judgement calls were highly constrained – even for the best of the best. Weight was the sworn enemy for such a journey, yet Apollo 11

carried more than 30kg of emergency procedures. 'Follow the procedures' was thus the watchword for this extraordinary team

A problem with intuition?

There are many problems associated with intuitive approaches. Let's list them:

1. First, **the variability of results** between evaluators: between a fearful evaluator and a bold one the differences are immense. Within this wide gap, we also find those who want to earn dollars and those who strive to be more ethical, as very expensive technology can raise questions of conflict of interest. Here we should also mention Neville Fay, who developed the concept of *Defensive arboriculture*, which refers to cases where professional practices are more focused on self-protection against litigation than on accurate diagnosis and treatment.
2. This variability is linked to a **high sensitivity to judgement biases**: the assessment of a tree's likelihood of failure can shift dramatically depending on the imagined targets beneath it. Remove the targets and the failure likelihood is underestimated; place children beneath the tree and it is overestimated. There's an amusing anecdote mentioned in the excellent book *Noise* by Kahneman, Sibony and Sunstein: in the United States, judges

are more lenient on Mondays if their favourite basketball team won over the weekend. Let's not think we are immune to biases, as believing so is the best way to be steeped in them.

3. The **inability to explain, structure, and therefore justify a result**: an intuitive outcome is often accompanied by 'You must trust me.' All of this is, of course, neither scientific nor rigorous enough, and indefensible in front of anyone - let alone a judge (whose favourite team may have lost the day before).

4. And finally, if a result cannot be explained, it becomes **impossible to pass on evaluation methods to new generations**. All trainers in structural diagnostics have, of course, faced this obstacle. What can we truly convey in training if we rely solely on personal experience and outcomes based on intuition?

The challenges are numerous and deeply significant. If NASA and the justice system encounter issues associated with intuition, it seems only natural that arboriculture should too. Let us now examine how the medical field has responded to these challenges in dealing with health diagnoses. To do so, we will take an example from the history of medicine which offers valuable lessons and potential parallels.

Virginia Apgar's score

In 1952, Virginia Apgar, an obstetrics doctor, proposed a scoring method for assessing the vitality of newborn babies. In this field too differences in results between professionals were a problem. Resuscitated too late, monitored unnecessarily, or not monitored in time, newborn babies were exposed to intuitive decisions which came with all the predictable mistakes. Apgar realised that these differences were not acceptable and responded to the problem by giving structure to a judgement that was not previously structured. How did she do it?

Five parameters were selected. Note that she succeeded in making them stick to the letters of her name. Next, each parameter was assigned a gradient. Apgar defined three levels for each parameter, weighted as 0, 1 or 2 points (Figure 1). These points were then added together to calculate the total score, which was interpreted using a simple three-level results table (Figure 2).

There are two key points to note. Today, all children are scored by APGAR at birth. The score was created empirically 72 years ago and remains relevant today. Also, the medical field now produces 10,000 scientific publications each year on the topic of scoring systems. There are scores for all types of issue that require evaluation: health status, organ function, phenomena, urgency levels, disease progression, and more. Every day, scores are debated or discarded, others are invented, and some are improved. 10,000 publications - proof that evaluation methods are taken very seriously.

In arboriculture, the issue of intuition and methods that combine multiple parameters does not yet seem to be fully explored - or even questioned. Too few methods are currently available and applicable in the field. As a result, arborists predominantly rely on intuition, which often leads, quite understandably, to an over-reliance on the technological model, which, let's not forget, can also be a powerful source of diagnostic errors. Arboriculture must do better than this.

The post-VTA era

Although the VTA method was necessary in its day to improve the qualitative assessment of the structural condition of trees, it now seems outdated, not because of its shortcomings but because it does not precisely define the method for obtaining a result. We maintain that by studying how other professions have addressed similar challenges, the future of 'basic assessment' will be to evolve into 'clinical assessment', which is already widely referenced, scientifically solid and accompanied by scores to produce defined results - that is, numerous scores for evaluating various tree parts including fork scores, cavity scores, root system scores, scores for environmental modifications and many more.

Indicator		0 Points	1 Point	2 Points
A	Activity (muscle tone)	Absent	Flexed limbs	Active
P	Pulse	Absent	< 100 BPM	> 100 BPM
G	Grimace (reflex irritability)	Floppy	Minimal response to stimulation	Prompt response to stimulation
A	Appearance (skin color)	Blue Pale	Pink body Blue extremities	Pink
R	Respiration	Absent	Slow and irregular	Vigorous cry

Figure 1

Score	
7 to 10	Baby appears to be normal on the APGAR score.
4 to 6	Intervention is needed until the baby's APGAR score is a 7.
0 to 3	The baby requires immediate attention, resuscitation, and other treatment.

Figure 2

It should be pointed out that procedural sequences do not limit complexity. They do not prevent us from thinking; on the contrary, they reinforce clinical reasoning. We should take inspiration from the medical field and NASA – if not for ourselves, who claim expertise, then for the next generations of arborists, who will need to assess trees and cannot afford to wait 30 years to gain experience. To do this, we need to become less approximate and more useful, and collectively develop new qualitative evaluation methods.

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